

SOME SUBJECTIVE REASONS TO CREATING A COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract: the competence of schools in the work and use of media and social networks as objective reasons for creating a competitive environment in schools is analyzed. It also shows the increase in the literacy of the school principal in terms of organizing and developing competitive relations in the school. In addition, the need to form competitive relations between teachers based on the results of trained students was explained.

Key words: school, competition, media and social networks, professional development, student results, teacher results.

There are unique challenges and obstacles in creating a competitive environment for effective organization and management of school education. It is important to determine the subjective reasons for creating a competitive environment at school.

In creating a competitive environment in schools, it is necessary to determine the impact of existing problems on the quality of education. Problems in creating a competitive environment in schools can simultaneously affect the competitive environment as several processes with subjective reasons.

Therefore, for this, it is important to identify the competitive entities that serve to create a competitive environment in schools, and to identify the internal and external factors and obstacles that affect the effective implementation of their tasks.

The subjects of competition that serve to create a competitive environment in schools are students, pedagogues and the school director, who implement and manage the competition process. Mass media are a special intermediary between the school and

the community, they help to inform the public about the plans or achievements of the school and to expand the circle of partners, sponsors, as well as to form a positive opinion about the school.

People receive the information they need based on their goals. For example, parents are interested in information about the conditions created in the school or the services provided (educational excursions, teaching additional subjects, sports, music, robotics, etc.). The media will highlight information about volunteer, community projects and charity events in order to attract the attention of partners and applicants in order to provide wider coverage of the school's social activities.

However, some schools do not have enough skills to work with mass media and social networks, as a result of which they cannot present their achievements or existing opportunities to the general public. This causes them to miss out on some opportunities to attract students or attract competitive educators to work in the school. Because it is necessary to saturate the interested persons and the public with the necessary information. If the public and stakeholders are not constantly informed about the achievements and opportunities of the schools through the media and social networks, it will be very difficult for them to compete with competitive schools in the education market.

All children up to the age of seven are admitted to the first grade, regardless of the maximum number of 35 students in the class or the lack of places. Schools do not compete with each other in this situation and fulfill their obligations under the law. However, for parents, it is not the number of students in the class, but the quality of education in the school and the conditions created for the students that are important.

The competence of the school director is important for creating or developing a competitive environment in the school. This requires determining the level of literacy of the school director on creating or developing a competitive environment. In a survey of school principals, 97 percent said that a school principal does not compete with anyone and why competition is important.

The question arises, what is the reason why there is no competitive motive among the principals of such schools? Such leaders, first of all, do not perform the task of ensuring competitiveness themselves as managers, and secondly, most of them are not prestigious or successful schools. Therefore, they cannot compete with others in the field of education. That is, the school shows the director's lack of desire to compete, that is, his lack of competence to organize competition in schools.

It can be seen that most of the school leaders do not have enough literacy on how to organize a competitive environment in schools.

This raises the question, how can the school director increase his competence in organizing and developing a competitive environment in schools? It is mandatory for employees to take professional development programs of a specified duration and collect a specified amount of credit points every year. The total annual duration of staff training is set to at least 30 hours for managers and specialists of the public education system, and at least 36 hours for pedagogical staff.[1.]

According to this, school principals improve their skills in 8 competencies based on a 30-hour curriculum and program. These include the following competencies:

management competence;

legal competence;

financial and economic competence;

communicative competence;

information communication technologies and media literacy competence;

competence of self- and personnel professional development;

competence of responsibility and flexibility;

competence to introduce inclusive education.[2.]

Among these competencies, there is no competence to organize and develop a competitive environment in schools. Therefore, it can be concluded that school leaders are not trained in the organization and development of competition environment in the training plans and programs of the training system.

Therefore, most school principals do not even have an understanding of the importance of competition in ensuring the quality of education in schools, or although some school principals know that competition is important, they lack the experience to implement it, that is, they do not know how to improve the quality of education by creating an environment of competition in practice. Currently, the inability of school principals to organize or develop a competitive environment in their management means that they do not have the competence to organize a competitive environment.

It is important to create an atmosphere of competition between pedagogues and staff in schools. This, in turn, serves to increase the quality of education and fill the school with potential personnel. In the school, the pedagogue ensures the stability of the staff. According to a survey conducted among school principals, "Is competition between teachers organized?" to the question, all the school principals answered "yes", but when asked how it was organized, only 18 percent gave their opinion on the organization of competition among pedagogues, even then the answers were not given completely. It can be concluded that the atmosphere of competition among pedagogues does not exist at the school level. Because it shows that there is no clear strategy of competition between pedagogues in the school administration, about the indicators on which the pedagogues compete, the purpose and tasks of the competition, which ensures quality efficiency.

Competitive pedagogues not only serve to improve the quality of school education, but also contribute to increasing the school's reputation as a fundamental preparation for external evaluation of education.

According to the legislation, when determining the rating of general secondary educational institutions, schools are evaluated based on the indicator of the level of foreign language knowledge of pedagogues (10 points) and the indicators of the quality (competence) of pedagogues (20 points). 30 points out of 100 points are allocated for the level of foreign language knowledge and competence of pedagogic personnel. [3.]

The evaluation criterion is determined based on the number of teachers with national or equivalent international certification at B2 level and above. Competence is determined according to the categories of pedagogues. The question arises as to how accurate it is to assign a rating in an external evaluation? Do these indicators have an impact on the quality of education? there are several questions. In general, the situation is approached one-sidedly. When studying the performance of teachers with B2 and higher national or equivalent international certificates, these certificates only determine their knowledge, although the goal is to improve the quality of education, and their impact on students' knowledge is hardly noticed. Because there is almost no difference between the knowledge of students of a pedagogue with and without a certificate. Therefore, it is appropriate to revise the parameters of this indicator.

At the same time, evaluation according to categories of pedagogues does not affect the quality of education. This situation was shown as a result of experiment. In particular, the knowledge of students taught by 120 concrete and natural science pedagogues during one academic year was tested in Navoi region. According to the results of the test, the students who showed the highest indicators are students of pedagogues without this category or of the second category. All students of some higher category or first category pedagogues did not pass the tests at all. There is a significant difference between the category of teachers and the performance of their students.[4.]

Having categories for teachers can only help improve their financial status as personal achievements, but it does not serve to ensure the competitiveness of teachers in improving the quality of education. Getting a category is defined as an obligation for pedagogues. Getting a category is done not to ensure the quality of education for the pedagogue, but to fulfill the obligation within the specified period or to increase the monthly salary. Therefore, there is no competition between pedagogues to get a category in the school, and this does not lead to ensuring the competitiveness of pedagogues in school education. The competitiveness of educators should be

determined not by their personal achievements, but by the results of their consumers, that is, the students they teach.

In conclusion, there are the following main problems in creating and developing a competitive environment at school:

the skills of schools in working with and using media and social networks in the development of competitive relations are insufficient;

there is no professional development course for the school director, which serves to increase the literacy of the school director in terms of organization and development of competition;

Since the activities of pedagogues are evaluated based on a one-sided approach with their personal achievements, there is no competitive relationship regarding the results of the students taught by them.

The development of competitive relations in school education requires the search for resources to create a competitive environment.

References

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